

Ewepa 2011 - XII European Workshop on Efficiency and Productivity Analysis - Verona - Italy

Book of abstracts

Contents

Program committee	14
Program	15
List of abstracts	35
Precise efficiency score estimation by using Data Envelopment and Stochastic Frontier Analysis - A systematic comparison and an evaluation of simple approaches to combine efficiency estimates, <i>Mark ANDOR, Frederik Hesse, (Discussant: Finn Førsund)</i>	35
Measuring Capital for Micro and Small Enterprises in Indonesia, <i>Anne Prestvik, (Discussant: Christine Amsler)</i>	36
Consistent estimation of a true fixed-effects stochastic frontier model, <i>Federico BELOTTI, Giuseppe Ilardi, (Discussant: William Horrace)</i>	36
Demand uncertain, excess of capacity and allocative efficiency: an application to the Spanish Port Authorities in the period 1986-2007, <i>Soraya HIDALGO-GALLEGO, Ramón Núñez-Sánchez, (Discussant: Sergio Perelman)</i>	37
Does weather matter on efficiency and productivity? An empirical analysis of the Electricity Distribution Market in South America, <i>Karim Anaya, (Discussant: Philippe Vanden Eeckaut)</i>	37
How to compete in the Higher Education Market? - Empirical Evidence for Economies of Scale and Scope of German Higher Education Institutions, <i>Maria OLIVARES, Heike Wetzel, (Discussant: Gary Ferrier)</i>	38
Separating Environmental Efficiency into Production and Abatement Efficiency - A Nonparametric Model With Application To U.S. Power Plants, <i>Benjamin Hampf, (Discussant: Timo Kuosmanen)</i>	39
The US Agriculture Greenhouse Emissions and Environmental Performance, <i>Tshepelayi Kabata, (Discussant: Shawna Grosskopf)</i>	40
Analysis of the Effects of Soil Organic Matter (SOM) on Efficiency and Agricultural Productivity, <i>Kepifri Lakoh, (Discussant: Sergio Destefanis)</i>	40
Information Technology and the International Productivity Gaps, <i>Tero Kuusi, (Discussant: Robert Russell)</i>	41
An analysis of ICT-enabled innovation in Norwegian firms: Are ICT users more innovative?, <i>Marina Rybalka, (Discussant: Jaap Bos)</i>	42
An efficiency approach to innovation systems, <i>Monica MIhaela Matei, (Discussant: Cinzia Daraio)</i>	43
Classic and bayesian stochastic frontier analysis for the Italian water sector, <i>Valeria Di Cosmo, (Discussant: Mike Tsionas)</i>	43

Decomposing Economic Inefficiency in a Revenue setting: The Norwegian Ground Fishery, Kristin Helen Roll	105
Monitoring the productivity change of retailing stores, Clara VAZ, Ana Camanho S.	106
The Relationship Between Technical Efficiency and Industrial Concentration : Evidence from the Indone- sian Food and Beverages Industry, Maman SETIAWAN, Grigorios Emvalomatis, Alfons Oude Lansink	106
FDI productivity spillover and technological gap in small versus large establishments in the Malaysian manufacturing sector, Noor Aini KHALIFAH, Salmah Mohd Salleh	107
Technical Change vs Efficiency Change: How do Food Industries Evolve over Time, Christophe BONTEMPS, Céline Nauges, Vincent Requillart, Michel Simioni	108
Estimation and Inference in Parametric Deterministic Frontier Models, Christine AMSLER, Michael Leonard, Peter Schmidt	109
A State Contingent Approach to Estimating Efficiency under Production Uncertainty, Teresa Serra, Robert G. Chambers, Spiro E. STEFANOU	110
Expected Ranks in Parametric Frontier Models, William HORRACE, Seth Richards-Shubik	111
Estimation and Decomposition of Inefficiency when Producers Maximize Return to the Outlay, Subal C. KUMBHAKAR, Frank Asche, Ragnar Tveteras	111
Common sets of weights as summaries of DEA profiles of weights, Nuria RAMON, José L. Ruiz, Inmaculada Sirvent	111
On the uniqueness issue of the slacks-based network DEA efficiency scores, Miki TSUTSUI, Kaoru Tone	112
Choosing weights of extreme efficient DMUs in DEA: A comparison of some proposals with application to the Spanish banking sector, Begona GONZALEZ-PEREZ, Enrique Lopez-Gonzalez, Cristina Mendana-Cuervo	113
On the non-oriented epsilon-based measure of efficiency in DEA, Kaoru TONE, Miki Tsutsui	113
Bounded Radial Models, Jesus T. PASTOR, Mette Asmild, Juan Aparicio, Javier Alcaraz	114
Benchmarking countries environmental performance, Andreia ZANELLA, Ana S. Camanho, Teresa G. Dias	115
Measurement of environmental productivity and efficiency in the steam power generation of the Japanese electric utility firms, Jiro NEMOTO, Akiko Okamoto	115
Eco-efficiency and convergence in OECD countries, Mariam CAMARERO, Juana Castillo-Giménez, Andrés Picazo-Tadeo, Cecilio Tamarit	116
Electric Utilities, Environmental Externalities and Cost Measured Productivity Growth, Gerald Granderson, Diego PRIOR	117
Solow Residuals: Decomposition into Frontier and Excess Capacity Components, Betty DANIEL, Christain Hafner, Hans Manner, Léopold Simar	118
Comparative analysis of the Energy dependency, Efficiency and Productivity of the Manufacturing Indus- tries: the case of Iran, Ali EMAMI MEIBODI, Mojtaba Esfandiari Kaloukan, Zahra Zakeri	118
Efficiency of Factor Allocation and Aggregate Productivity: Cross-Country Evidence in Manufacturing, Addisu Abebe Lashitew	119
The Sources of Productivity Change in the Major Sectors of the U.S. Economy, Christopher O'Donnell	120
The optimal allocation of resources for secondary education schools, Carla HAELERMANS, Kristof De Witte, Jos Blank	120

Choosing weights of extreme efficient DMUs in DEA: A comparison of some proposals with application to the Spanish banking sector

Begona GONZALEZ-PEREZ, Enrique Lopez-Gonzalez, Cristina Mendana-Cuervo

Advanced DEA II

This paper is focused on the analysis of one limitation of the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) and the effects of some proposals which try to solve it. The extensive use of DEA has demonstrated that it has a lot of advantages but it also has some limitations. An important drawback is related to the Decision Making Units (DMUs) which generate the efficient frontier, the extreme efficient DMUs. They have alternative optimal sets of weights or multipliers for their variables and only one set should be chosen. Although few authors have dealt with this question, there are some proposals which try to solve it. In this sense, we analyze the problem along with some of the formulations proposed to solve it and we apply two of these proposals in order to shed light on their effects on the weights of extreme efficient DMUs and compare them. The extreme efficient DMUs are the vertices of the efficient frontier, so they have infinite supporting hyperplanes which define infinite alternative sets of weights in the multiplier formulation of DEA. However, the efficiency measurement and other utilities of DEA, like a benchmarking tool, a ranking methodology or a method for identifying groups, require choosing only one set of weights. Many authors have ignored this problem and have opted for the first solution of the DEA model, while other researchers have tried to solve the previous limitation by means of different DEA formulations. In this paper we focus on two of these proposals. On one hand, Adu (2001), who uses the cross efficiency concept and the geometrical interpretation of DEA, proposes a DEA model to choose the set of weights associated to the supporting hyperplane which differentiates the specific extreme efficient DMU as much as possible from the rest of the closest extreme efficient DMUs. She tries to select the weights by which the extreme efficient DMU is better than the other ones, i.e., she emphasizes the best different performance of each extreme efficient DMU. On the other hand, Cooper et al. (2007) also select the optimal weights set according to the geometrical interpretation of the multiplier DEA formulation. They propose a two-stage mixed integer linear programming to choose the weights which are associated with the face of the frontier of higher possible dimension to which the extreme efficient DMU belongs, i.e, they select the coefficients of the supporting hyperplane which contains the maximum number of extreme efficient DMUs. In this paper, we apply both formulations to the Spanish Banking Sector in order to know the effects of the two previous proposals but before it, we use the super efficiency DEA model (Andersen y Petersen, 1993) in order to differentiate between efficient and inefficient DMUs and get the first combination of weights of every extreme efficient DMUs. Finally, we compare the weights which have been obtained in the three formulations by means of non-parametric tests and we can observe that the differences among them are statistically significant.

On the non-oriented epsilon-based measure of efficiency in DEA

Kaoru TONE, Miki Tsutsui

Advanced DEA II

In this paper, we present the non-oriented (i.e. both input- and output-oriented) version of the epsilon-based measure of efficiency (EBM) in DEA and point to a strange property of the model that the constant returns-to scale model and the variable returns-to-scale model yield the same efficiency score. We clarify this phenomenon and demonstrate how to get rid of such inconvenience. The unique features of this paper are (1) unification of radial and non-radial models in a single framework called EBM and (2) extension to the non-oriented case which is suitable for measuring both input-side and output-side inefficiencies simultaneously. In DEA, we have two typical measures of technical efficiency with different characteristics: radial and non-radial. Historically, the radial measure, represented

Choosing weights of extreme efficient DMUs in DEA: A comparison of some proposals with application to the Spanish banking sector

This paper is focused on the analysis of one limitation of Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) and the effects of some proposals which try to solve it. The extensive use of DEA has demonstrated that it has a lot of advantages but it also has some limitations. An important drawback is related to the Decision Making Units (DMUs) which generate the efficient frontier, the extreme efficient DMUs. They have alternative optimal sets of weights or multipliers for their variables and only one set should be chosen. Although few authors have dealt with this question, there are some proposals which try to solve it. In this sense, we analyze the problem along with two of the models proposed to solve it and we apply them in order to shed light on their effects on the weights of extreme efficient DMUs and compare them.

The extreme efficient DMUs are the vertexes of the efficient frontier, so they have infinite supporting hyperplanes which define infinite alternative sets of weights in the multiplier formulation of DEA. However, the efficiency measurement and other utilities of DEA, like a benchmarking tool, a ranking methodology or a method for identifying groups, require selecting only one set of weights. Many authors have ignored this problem and have chosen the first solution of the DEA model, while other researchers have tried to solve the previous limitation by means of different DEA formulations. In this paper we focus on two of these proposals.

On one hand, Adu (2001), who uses the cross-efficiency concept, proposes a DEA model to choose the set of weights associated to the supporting hyperplane which differentiates the specific extreme efficient DMU as much as possible from the rest of the closest extreme efficient DMUs. She tries to select the weights by which the extreme efficient DMU is better than the other ones, i.e., she emphasizes the best different performance of each extreme efficient DMU.

On the other hand, Cooper *et al.* (2007) proposed a two-stage mixed integer linear programming to choose the weights which are associated with the facet of the frontier of higher possible dimension to which the extreme efficient DMU belongs, i.e., they select the coefficients of the supporting hyperplane which contains the maximum number of extreme efficient DMUs.

In this paper, we apply both formulations to the Spanish banking sector in order to know the effects of the two previous proposals but before it, we use the super efficiency DEA model (Andersen y Petersen, 1993) in order to differentiate between efficient and inefficient DMUs and get the first combination of weights of every extreme efficient DMU. Finally, we compare the weights which have been obtained in the three formulations by means of non-parametric tests and we can observe that the differences among them are not always statistically significant.

Key words: Extreme efficient DMUs, weights selection, comparison of approaches

1. Introduction

Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is a nonparametric tool which generates a frontier in order to measure the relative efficiency of a set of Decision Making Units (DMUs). DEA is mainly formulated as an envelopment model or as a multiplier model, i.e., the primal and the dual expressions of linear optimization problem, so both of them get the same efficiency score but they provide different information: the multiplier model offers the weights or multipliers of the variables included as inputs and outputs and the envelopment model indicates the reference efficient DMUs for inefficient DMUs. Despite this fact, due to the complementary slackness condition, both types of models are related, so the weights from the multiplier model have a direct relationship with the slacks from the envelopment one.

Even though it's a powerful tool, the practical application of DEA has some important limitations. One of these weaknesses refers to the multiple alternative optimal sets of weights which might be obtained for the assessed DMUs from a multiplier DEA model. In optimization linear programming, degenerate solutions could appear. It means that the number of non-zero weights is fewer than the number of restrictions. It implies that the number of optimal sets of weights is infinite.

The previous limitation might affect to any type of DMUs, efficient and inefficient, although it is more frequent for extreme efficient DMUs, i.e., the vertices of the efficient frontier which defines it. They are also named as *E* DMUs (Charnes *et al.*, 1991). These type of DMUs define the efficient frontier because, by means of their union, they build different facets of the frontier. They usually contribute to expand more than one efficient facet and every facet usually has associated one particular set of weights for the variables (Olesen and Petersen, 2003), so an *E* DMU might be efficient with different multipliers in its variables. This is the reason why extreme efficient DMUs might have more than one unique set of weights.

The Fig. 1 illustrates the previous situation when there are three extreme efficient DMUs (A, B and C) for a two outputs-one input process. As seen, there are several hyperplanes associated with B, so many as there are between A and C (Cooper *et al.*, 2007).

Fig. 1.

If efficient scores are the objective, the previous limitation is not a great problem, but when the multipliers are used to obtain additional information about variables, for example, their relative importance or their contribution of every input and output to the efficient score, it

becomes a serious limitation. So, the weights or multipliers of extreme efficient DMUs should be chosen with an appropriate and reasonable criterion, not randomly or arbitrarily.

Most of the authors have usually ignored the multiple optimal sets of weights and they have chosen the first solution obtained (Roll y Golani, 1993). In fact, there are few authors who deal with this problem explicitly. In this sense, Rosen *et al.* (1998), Adu (2001), Cooper *et al.* (2007) and Badini *et al.* (2009) have done the main contributions. However, the solutions they have suggested have different basis, so they might also lead to different sets of optimal weights.

In order to test the possible differences, we specifically focus on Adu (2001) and Cooper *et al.* (2007) approaches. Our objective is to compare the solutions obtained from the models they have proposed to select the most appropriate set of weights for extreme efficient DMUs. We also compare them with the super-efficiency DEA model which obtains a unique solution due to the exclusion of the assessed DMU (Andersen y Petersen, 1993).

The content of the rest of the paper is organised as follows. Following this introduction, the next section is focused in explained theoretical basis of the approaches proposed by Adu (2001) and Cooper *et al.* (2007) to select a suitable set of weights for extreme efficient DMUs. In the third section the super-efficiency model and the previous approaches are applied to the Spanish banking sector and then the results are compared. The final section is about the main conclusions.

2. Theoretical aspects

Adu (2001), based on cross-efficiency model (Sexton *et al.*, 1986), developed an approach to select one of the several sets of optimal weights associated with extreme efficient DMUs.

The cross-efficiency score of a DMU j is measured with its own inputs $x_j = (x_{1j}, x_{2j}, \dots, x_{mj})$ and outputs $y_j = (y_{1j}, y_{2j}, \dots, y_{sj})$ but with the weights that the DMU k has obtained for those variables, i.e., $v_k = (v_{1k}, v_{2k}, \dots, v_{mk})$ and $\mu_k = (\mu_{1k}, \mu_{2k}, \dots, \mu_{sk})$. So, the cross efficiency is

$$\text{defined as } CE_{kj} = \frac{\sum_{r=1}^s \mu_{rk} Y_{rj}}{\sum_{i=1}^m v_{ik} X_{ij}}.$$

The weights of DMU k can be used for the rest of the DMUs of the sample and obtain the cross-efficiency scores for all of them. So, all the cross-efficiency scores can be shown by means of a matrix where each row shows the efficiency scores of all DMUs using the weights of DMU k , while each column shows the efficiency score of DMU j with the weights of the rest of the DMUs. Therefore, the final cross-efficiency score of the organization j could be calculated as

$$\text{the arithmetic mean of that column, this is, } \overline{CE}_j = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n CE_{kj}.$$

j	1	2	3	...	n
1	CE_{11}	CE_{12}	CE_{13}	...	CE_{1n}
2	CE_{21}	CE_{22}	CE_{23}	...	CE_{2n}
...
n	CE_{n1}	CE_{n2}	CE_{n3}	...	CE_{nn}
	\overline{CE}_1	\overline{CE}_2	\overline{CE}_3	...	\overline{CE}_n

The cross-efficiency matrix is useful in order to determine the efficiency scores of DMUs from the perspective of other DMUs but the model does not generate new weights for inputs and outputs (Li and Reeves, 1999). However, the perspective of other DMUs might be used to select the set of weights for extreme efficient DMUs. Every multiplier model includes a restriction which measures the gap between the outputs and the inputs of every DMU in the sample, i.e., the inputs and outputs are weighted by the multipliers of the assessed DMU k , this

$$\text{is, } \sum_{r=1}^s \mu_{rk} Y_{rj} - \sum_{i=1}^m v_{ik} X_{ij} \leq 0. \text{ So, this can be expressed as } \alpha_{kj} = \sum_{i=1}^m v_{ik} X_{ij} - \sum_{r=1}^s \mu_{rk} Y_{rj}.$$

Then, according to Adu (2001), α_{kj} is very similar to the cross-efficiency score of the DMU j with DMU k . Furthermore, α_{kj} is a linear expression, so its use is easier than the cross-efficiency measure. Considering this, Adu (2001) proposed a model which, for every extreme efficient DMU, selects the weights based on the maximum possible differentiation respect to the rest of extreme efficient DMUs. Her approach is shown in Model 1.

Model 1.

$$\max z$$

Subject to :

$$z - \alpha_{kj} \leq 0 \quad \forall j \in E$$

$$\sum_{r=1}^s \mu_{rk} Y_{rj} - \sum_{i=1}^m v_{ik} X_{ij} + \alpha_{kj} = 0 \quad \forall j \in E$$

$$\sum_{r=1}^s \mu_{rk} Y_{rk} = 1$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m v_{ik} X_{ik} = 1$$

$$z, \alpha_{kj}, v_{ik}, \mu_{rk} \geq 0 \quad \forall j, i, r$$

Every time the previous model is solving, z gets the maximum possible value, so it is equal or less than α_{kj} , and α_{kj} will have a non-negative value equal to the difference between outputs and inputs of DMU j weighted by the multipliers of DMU k . So the second restrictions of the model try to find the maximum difference between extreme efficient DMUs, and if they have a null value, the gap between DMUs k and DMU j is also zero, but it only happens if it is the same DMU. Finally, the third and fourth restrictions ensure that the assessed DMU is an extreme efficient one.

The reasoning of Adu (2001) is also shown in Fig. 2, where three DMUs (A, B and C) define the efficient frontier for a two output-one input problem. Two of the possible sets of weights are associated with two facets or hyperplanes: one hyperplane connects A and B and the other one connects B and C. Both segments are facets of the efficient frontier. The segment between A and B represents the set of weights for DMU B which also makes efficient DMU A. The segment between M and M' represents another one of the infinite number of possible hyperplanes between A and B, and between B and C, whose slopes define an optimal set of weights for DMU B.

One possible solution for multiple sets of weights is to choose the set which makes the assessed DMU better than other DMUs. So, DMU B should differ as much as possible from the others ones, i.e., maximize the distance with other DMUs on the frontier. The set of weights that makes B better than other ones is associated with the slope of the hyperplane which pass through B, which has the maxim distance from the nearest organizations, A and C. As shown in Fig. 2, the difference between them is higher for the segment projected between A and A' and between C and C', which represent the efficiency for DMUs A and C, respectively, when the weights of DMU B are considered. Therefore, the maximum differentiation of DMU B from the rest of DMUs is analogous to maximize α_{kj} , so the minimum value of the cross-efficiency scores between B and A or between B and C should be maximum.

Figura 2.

Meanwhile, Cooper et al. (2007) proposed a two-step model in order to select the optimal weights associated with the facet of the efficient frontier of highest dimension. From a geometric perspective, this means that it selects the optimal set of weights which the maximum support from the data: for every efficient DMU, this approach selects the weights of the hyperplane that maximizes the contact with the production possibility set, i.e., with the highest number of extreme efficient DMUs. The first step of their approach is shown in Model 2.

Model 2 is a mixed integer linear optimization problem because the variable only can take the values 0 or 1. As in the previous approach, the first and second restrictions ensures that the assessed DMU is an extreme efficient one. For every extreme efficient DMU k under assess, the third restriction is used to get the maximum support from the rest of the extreme efficient DMUs.

If M is a positive value previously fixed, as many $t_j = 0$, many $l_j = 0$, so DMU j belongs to the hyperplane of highest dimension $\sum_{r=1}^s \mu_r y_{rj} - \sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{ij} = 0$. As the optimization problem tries to minimize $\sum_{j \in E} l_j$, it gets the highest number of $l_j = 0$ and, accordingly, $t_j = 0$. So, the assessed DMU selects the hyperplane which has the highest contact with the rest of the extreme efficient DMUs.

Model 2.

$$\min I_k = \sum_{j \in E} I_j$$

Subject to :

$$\sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{ik} = 1$$

$$\sum_{r=1}^s \mu_r y_{rk} = 1$$

$$\sum_{r=1}^s \mu_r y_{rj} - \sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{i0} + t_j = 0 \quad \forall j \in E$$

$$t_j - M I_j \leq 0 \quad \forall j \in E$$

$$I_j \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall j \in E$$

$$v_i, \mu_r, t_j \geq 0 \quad \forall i, r, j$$

This reasoning is shown in Fig. 3. For the same example than the previous one, for DMU B this model selects the weights associated with the segment between A and B or between D and C, because they are supported for more real extreme efficient DMUs. The hyperplanes of these facets are preferable than the others because these last ones are only supported by DMU B. Therefore, the weights chosen belong to the facet to which the DMU assessed contributes to expand and its dimension is the highest possible.

Figure 3.

Cooper *et al.* (2007) also proposed a second step to ensure positive weights for all variables and this is shown in Model 3. It maximizes the minimum value of the virtual variables, so it tries to maximize the contribution of the virtual variables to the efficient score. Model 3 uses the results obtained for Model 2, but it also maximizes the relative value of the virtual weights. Due

to this fact, it includes as many additional restriction as inputs and outputs represents the production function.

Modelo 3.

$$\max z_0$$

Subject to :

$$\sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{i0} = 1$$

$$\sum_{r=1}^s \mu_r y_{r0} = 1$$

$$\sum_{r=1}^s \mu_r y_{rj} - \sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{i0} + t_j = 0 \quad \forall j \in E$$

$$t_j - Ml_j \leq 0 \quad \forall j \in E$$

$$\sum_{j \in E} l_j = l_j^*$$

$$v_i x_{i0} \geq z_0 \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

$$\mu_r y_{r0} \geq z_0 \quad r = 1, 2, \dots, s$$

$$l_j \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall j \in E$$

$$v_i, \mu_r, t_j \geq 0 \quad \forall i, r, j$$

3. Empirical application

In order to test the possible difference among the solutions obtained from the previous approaches, we applied the models proposed to the Spanish banking industry. The banking sector is the centre of a lot of analysis because it plays a very important role in the running of the economy. Besides, the efficiency of banks has also been studying by many authors by applying DEA (Pastor *et al.*, 1997; Lozano-Vivas *et al.*, 2002; Prior and Surroca, 2006).

The variables which reflect the bank activity are classified as inputs and outputs. On one hand, the input variables are:

- Personnel expenses / Gross Margin (PE_I)
- Depreciation expenses / Gross Margin (DE_I)
- Other management expenses / Gross Margin (OME_I)

On the other side, the output variables are:

- Treasury /Financial investments (T_O)
- Credit loans / Financial investments (CL_O)
- Portfolio of securities / Financial investments (PS_O)
- Deposits from customers / Total liabilities (D_O)
- Deposits in credit entities (assets) / Total liabilities (DCEA_O)
- Deposits from credit entities (liabilities) / Total liabilities (DCEL_O)
- Commissions due to financial services / Interest income (C_O)

We want to stress some important aspects. The variables are expressed in ratio form, so the constant return to scale DEA models were used. Besides, due to the context, we selected the

output orientation for the DEA models. Lastly, in order to avoid prior standardization of the variables and problems associated with simple weights, like non-independence of units of measurement, we preferred to compare virtual variables, which are units independent. In this sense, as the models had output orientation, only the virtual outputs might be compared directly because their addition is equal to 1 for efficient and inefficient DMUs. But it does not happen with the virtual inputs of inefficient DMUs. So, to get comparable virtual inputs, we decided to divide every virtual input of every bank by its efficiency score and the addition of the virtual inputs of every bank will be also 1.

In 2008 there were 155 private banks in Spain but 89 were foreign branches, so these ones were excluded. The DMUs compared should use the same technology and they should be the most similar as possible, so we also excluded the banks with a null Herfindahl – Hirschman index, which measures the geographical concentration of the bank branches. A null index means that the geographical expansion is minimum and less similar to the rest of the banks with a higher expansion. After this, 11 banks were deleted from the original sample.

Besides, outliers and very influential DMUs were deleted in order to avoid distorted solutions. DEA is a frontier technique, so if there are outliers among the efficient DMUs, the rest might be compared with unachievable DMUs. Because of these reason, we build a reasonable frontier with the Prior and Surroca (2006) approach, which is an iterative variation of the process propped by Wilson (1995), who used the super-efficiency DEA model to detect and delete outliers. After this process, 7 banks were excluded.

After all the previous process the final sample was compound of 33 banks.

Firstly, the super-efficiency constant returns to scale model was applied because if a DMU is efficient by means of this model, is an extreme efficient DMU (Thrall, 1996). The super-efficiency scores obtained with this model are shown in Table 1. The number of banks classified as extreme efficient DMUs was 19 because their super-efficiency scores have a value lower than 1.

Table 1. Super-efficiency scores of banks

Bank	Score	Banks	Score
BANCO BILBAO VIZCAYA ARGENTARIA	0,531	URQUIJO SABADELL BANCA PRIVADA	1,397
BANCO ESPAÑOL DE CRÉDITO	0,831	POPULAR BANCA PRIVADA	0,806
BANCO SABADELL	1,228	FINANZIA, BANCO DE CRÉDITO	0,473
BANCO POPULAR ESPAÑOL	0,831	BANKOIA	1,243
BANKINTER	1,057	BANCO DE MADRID	1,683
BARCLAYS BANK	1,691	BANCA PUEYO	0,843
BANCO PASTOR	0,836	BANCO INVERSI	0,467
BANCO DE VALENCIA	0,905	BANCO DE FINANZAS E INVERSIONES	0,875
BANCO DE ANDALUCÍA	0,651	BANCO PEQUEÑA Y MEDIANA EMPRESA	1,766
BANCO GUIPUZCOANO	1,063	UBS BANK	1,136
BANCA MARCH	1,375	ALTAE BANCO	1,163
BANCO GALLEGO	2,110	BANCO ETCHEVERRÍA	0,379
BANCO BANIF	0,633	BANCO HALIFAX HISPANIA	0,913
GENERAL ELECTRIC CAPITAL BANK	0,621	BANCOFAR	0,780
RBC DEXIA INVESTOR SERVICES ESPAÑA	0,700	BANCO FINANZIA SOFINLOC	1,413
BANCO CAIXA GERAL	1,302	BNP PARIBAS ESPAÑA	0,457
CITIBANK ESPAÑA	0,497		

The super-efficiency model got a set of virtual inputs and the virtual outputs for extreme efficient banks with and they are shown in Table 2. Although this model obtains a unique set of weights, there were a lot of virtual weights with zero values because the simple multipliers were

also null. This is a great problem because, by applying the super-efficiency model, some of the variables were ignored in the weighting process.

Table 2. Virtual variables with super-efficiency model

	PE_I	DE_I	OME_I	T_O	CL_O	PS_O	D_O	DCEA_O	DCEL_O	C_O
BANCO BILBAO VIZCAYA ARGENTARIA	0,000 0	0,580 0	0,4200	0,000 0	0,000 0	1,000 0	0,000 0	0,0000	0,0000	0,000 0
BANCO ESPAÑOL DE CRÉDITO	0,000 0	0,000 0	1,0000	0,132 5	0,000 0	0,368 2	0,000 0	0,3344	0,1649	0,000 0
BANCO POPULAR ESPAÑOL	0,568 0	0,000 0	0,4320	0,081 8	0,000 0	0,242 2	0,510 8	0,0872	0,0000	0,078 1
BANCO PASTOR	0,000 0	0,000 0	1,0000	0,129 9	0,809 3	0,060 8	0,000 0	0,0000	0,0000	0,000 0
BANCO DE VALENCIA	0,000 0	0,356 6	0,6434	0,000 0	0,686 3	0,216 9	0,096 9	0,0000	0,0000	0,000 0
BANCO DE ANDALUCÍA	0,284 6	0,681 6	0,0338	0,046 0	0,857 5	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,0282	0,0012	0,067 0
BANCO BANIF	0,258 8	0,000 0	0,7412	0,039 3	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,069 1	0,0776	0,4535	0,360 6
GENERAL ELECTRIC CAPITAL BANK	0,000 0	1,000 0	0,0000	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,259 7	0,740 4	0,0000	0,0000	0,000 0
RBC DEXIA INVESTOR SERVICES ESPAÑA	0,737 9	0,000 0	0,2621	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,085 9	0,153 8	0,7604	0,0000	0,000 0
CITIBANK ESPAÑA	0,860 5	0,139 5	0,0000	0,189 2	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,5181	0,2927	0,000 0
POPULAR BANCA PRIVADA	0,000 0	0,784 9	0,2151	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,153 7	0,000 0	0,8221	0,0000	0,024 2
FINANZIA, BANCO DE CRÉDITO	0,000 0	0,772 7	0,2273	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,0000	1,0000	0,000 0
BANCA PUEYO	1,000 0	0,000 0	0,0000	0,158 5	0,000 0	0,134 0	0,707 5	0,0000	0,0000	0,000 0
BANCO INVERDIS	1,000 0	0,000 0	0,0000	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,291 7	0,000 0	0,0000	0,0000	0,708 3
BANCO DE FINANZAS E INVERSIONES	0,000 0	1,000 0	0,0000	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,674 3	0,000 0	0,0000	0,0000	0,325 7
BANCO ETCHEVERRÍA	0,000 0	0,428 5	0,5715	1,000 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,0000	0,0000	0,000 0
BANCO HALIFAX HISPANIA	0,797 1	0,000 0	0,2029	0,258 4	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,0000	0,7417	0,000 0
BANCOFAR	0,186 1	0,000 0	0,8139	0,000 0	0,438 5	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,0000	0,5615	0,000 0
BNP PARIBAS ESPAÑA	0,000 0	1,000 0	0,0000	0,000 0	0,126 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,0000	0,0212	0,852 8
Mín.	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,0000	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,0000	0,0000	0,000 0
Máx.	1,000 0	1,000 0	1,0000	1,000 0	0,857 5	1,000 0	0,740 4	0,8221	1,0000	0,852 8
Media	0,299 6	0,354 9	0,3454	0,107 1	0,153 6	0,183 5	0,119 9	0,1383	0,1703	0,127 2
Desv. Est.	0,396 0	0,407 6	0,3652	0,230 3	0,300 1	0,264 7	0,244 3	0,2672	0,3012	0,254 8

Table 3 shows the virtual variables for extreme efficient banks from the approach proposed by Adu (2001). As in super-efficiency model, some null weight was obtained for every extreme efficient bank.

Table 3. Virtual weights with Adu (2001)'s approach

	PE_I	DE_I	OME_I	T_O	CL_O	PS_O	D_O	DCEA_O	DCEL_O	C_O
BANCO BILBAO VIZCAYA ARGENTARIA	0,000 0	0,614 1	0,3859	0,105 6	0,000 0	0,760 3	0,000 0	0,0000	0,1340	0,000 0
BANCO ESPAÑOL DE CRÉDITO	0,000 0	0,310 4	0,6896	0,228 4	0,034 2	0,371 3	0,000 0	0,0828	0,2833	0,000 0
BANCO POPULAR ESPAÑOL	0,000 0	0,380 6	0,6194	0,244 8	0,060 0	0,318 2	0,000 0	0,2339	0,1431	0,000 0
BANCO PASTOR	0,000 0	0,364 5	0,6355	0,185 3	0,580 7	0,160 2	0,000 0	0,0000	0,0738	0,000 0
BANCO DE VALENCIA	0,000 0	0,545 8	0,4542	0,000 0	0,645 1	0,250 5	0,000 0	0,0000	0,1044	0,000 0
BANCO DE ANDALUCÍA	0,000 0	0,116 0	0,8840	0,000 0	0,718 2	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,2103	0,0715	0,000 0
BANCO BANIF	0,000 0	0,560 2	0,4398	0,049 9	0,151 7	0,093 2	0,000 0	0,0000	0,3816	0,323 6
GENERAL ELECTRIC CAPITAL BANK	0,000 0	0,735 4	0,2646	0,039 7	0,000 0	0,328 3	0,631 8	0,0000	0,0002	0,000 0
RBC DEXIA INVESTOR SERVICES ESPAÑA	0,075 5	0,332 5	0,5920	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,339 8	0,6505	0,0097	0,000 0
CITIBANK ESPAÑA	0,000 0	0,876 3	0,1237	0,193 1	0,244 0	0,111 7	0,000 0	0,3552	0,0959	0,000 0
POPULAR BANCA PRIVADA	0,000 0	0,187 3	0,8127	0,054 5	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,8664	0,0791	0,000 0
FINANZIA, BANCO DE CRÉDITO	0,619 6	0,098 1	0,2823	0,000 1	0,022 0	0,037 8	0,000 0	0,0000	0,9401	0,000 0
BANCA PUEYO	0,200 3	0,799 7	0,0000	0,206 6	0,000 0	0,238 9	0,549 1	0,0000	0,0054	0,000 0
BANCO INVERDIS	0,203 2	0,596 9	0,1999	0,049 7	0,000 0	0,343 2	0,000 0	0,0000	0,0103	0,596 8
BANCO DE FINANZAS E INVERSIONES	0,000 0	0,986 8	0,0132	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,571 3	0,157 2	0,2139	0,0000	0,057 6
BANCO ETCHEVERRÍA	0,000 0	0,947 8	0,0522	0,592 3	0,337 0	0,070 5	0,000 0	0,0000	0,0003	0,000 0
BANCO HALIFAX HISPANIA	0,369 6	0,256 7	0,3738	0,227 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,0000	0,7730	0,000 0
BANCOFAR	0,000 0	0,000 0	1,0000	0,000 0	0,075 5	0,000 5	0,000 0	0,0000	0,9241	0,000 0
BNP PARIBAS ESPAÑA	0,000 0	1,000 0	0,0000	0,000 0	0,196 4	0,186 1	0,000 0	0,0000	0,0799	0,537 6
Mín.	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,0000	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,000 0	0,0000	0,0000	0,000 0
Máx.	0,619 6	1,000 0	1,0000	0,592 3	0,718 2	0,760 3	0,631 8	0,8664	0,9401	0,596 8
Media	0,077 3	0,511 0	0,4117	0,114 6	0,161 3	0,202 2	0,088 3	0,1375	0,2163	0,079 8

Desv. Est.	0,165 7	0,317 3	0,3101	0,149 1	0,238 1	0,210 8	0,196 2	0,2463	0,3122	0,187 4
------------	------------	------------	--------	------------	------------	------------	------------	--------	--------	------------

Finally, the virtual variables which were obtained from the two-step process proposed by Cooper *et al.* (2007) are shown in Table 4, i. e., the virtual weights obtain from Model 2 (1) and from Model 3 (2). In the first step (1), some extreme efficient banks got zero virtual weights but it is because they are not situated in a full dimension efficient facet (FDEF), not because of the selected set of multipliers, as in the previous approaches.

Table 4. Virtual weights with Cooper *et al.* (2007)'s approach

		PE_I	DE_I	OME_I	T_O	CL_O	PS_O	D_O	DCEA_O	DCEL_O	C_O
BANCO BILBAO VIZCAYA ARGENTARIA	1	0.137	0.5112	0.3517	0.0718	0.1591	0.4427	0.0441	0.1769	0.0516	0.0538
	2	0.1371	0.5112	0.3517	0.0718	0.1591	0.4427	0.0441	0.1769	0.0516	0.0538
BANCO ESPAÑOL DE CRÉDITO	1	0.2593	0.0970	0.6437	0.1075	0.0691	0.3719	0.0000	0.3316	0.0000	0.1199
	2	0.2741	0.1016	0.6242	0.1407	0.0143	0.3808	0.0143	0.3219	0.0143	0.1136
BANCO POPULAR ESPAÑOL	1	0.1126	0.5904	0.2970	0.1626	0.2090	0.2408	0.0599	0.2038	0.0608	0.0630
	2	0.1126	0.5904	0.2970	0.1626	0.2090	0.2408	0.0599	0.2038	0.0608	0.0630
BANCO PASTOR	1	0.1905	0.0257	0.7838	0.1254	0.4409	0.0050	0.1796	0.0000	0.0000	0.2491
	2	0.2557	0.1500	0.5943	0.1506	0.5416	0.0881	0.0019	0.0019	0.0019	0.2140
BANCO DE VALENCIA	1	0.0000	0.3525	0.6475	0.0033	0.5816	0.2236	0.0000	0.0045	0.1369	0.0501
	2	0.0031	0.3516	0.6453	0.0031	0.5788	0.2238	0.0031	0.0045	0.1369	0.0498
BANCO DE ANDALUCÍA	1	0.1258	0.4369	0.4373	0.1717	0.3211	0.0671	0.0845	0.1760	0.0940	0.0856
	2	0.1258	0.4369	0.4373	0.1717	0.3211	0.0671	0.0845	0.1760	0.0940	0.0856
BANCO BANIF	1	0.0935	0.5598	0.3467	0.0545	0.1230	0.0857	0.0279	0.3625	0.1858	0.1605
	2	0.0935	0.5598	0.3467	0.0545	0.1230	0.0857	0.0279	0.3625	0.1858	0.1605
GENERAL ELECTRIC CAPITAL BANK	1	0.0000	0.8850	0.1150	0.0541	0.5540	0.3760	0.0000	0.0033	0.0001	0.0125
	2	0.0003	0.9995	0.0003	0.0415	0.0003	0.0003	0.9572	0.0003	0.0003	0.0003
RBC DEXIA INVESTOR SERVICES ESPAÑA	1	0.7962	0.0000	0.2038	0.0329	0.0003	0.0328	0.3746	0.4989	0.0034	0.0572
	2	0.1746	0.4145	0.4109	0.0323	0.0071	0.0477	0.1719	0.7264	0.0071	0.0076
CITIBANK ESPAÑA	1	0.0628	0.2601	0.6771	0.1124	0.0852	0.0470	0.0207	0.4981	0.1715	0.0650
	2	0.0628	0.2601	0.6771	0.1124	0.0852	0.0470	0.0207	0.4981	0.1715	0.0650
POPULAR BANCA PRIVADA	1	0.1562	0.4600	0.3838	0.0357	0.0078	0.1064	0.0341	0.7157	0.0334	0.0668
	2	0.1562	0.4600	0.3838	0.0357	0.0078	0.1064	0.0341	0.7157	0.0334	0.0668
FINANZIA. BANCO DE CRÉDITO	1	0.1439	0.2656	0.5905	0.0001	0.1545	0.0242	0.0067	0.4253	0.3563	0.0329
	2	0.1439	0.2656	0.5905	0.0001	0.1545	0.0242	0.0067	0.4253	0.3563	0.0329
BANCA PUEYO	1	0.7782	0.0000	0.2218	0.2338	0.0029	0.0679	0.5668	0.0828	0.0052	0.0406
	2	0.7761	0.0017	0.2222	0.2336	0.0017	0.0683	0.5678	0.0827	0.0052	0.0406
BANCO INVERDIS	1	0.1935	0.3758	0.4307	0.0511	0.0107	0.2531	0.0000	0.2467	0.0007	0.4377
	2	0.7273	0.0003	0.2723	0.0476	0.0003	0.1116	0.2549	0.1810	0.0038	0.4007
BANCO DE FINANZAS E INVERSIONES	1	0.5180	0.4820	0.0000	0.0495	0.0000	0.3985	0.1879	0.0261	0.0031	0.3349
	2	0.5159	0.4818	0.0023	0.0491	0.0023	0.3981	0.1847	0.0270	0.0023	0.3365
BANCO ETCHEVERRÍA	1	0.1366	0.5019	0.3615	0.6212	0.1955	0.0493	0.0681	0.0177	0.0003	0.0478
	2	0.1366	0.5019	0.3615	0.6212	0.1955	0.0493	0.0681	0.0177	0.0003	0.0478
BANCO HALIFAX HISPANIA	1	0.6200	0.1204	0.2596	0.2106	0.0977	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.6873	0.0041
	2	0.5617	0.1093	0.3290	0.2141	0.0650	0.0003	0.0002	0.0002	0.7201	0.0002
BANCOFAR	1	0.4167	0.3422	0.2410	0.0758	0.3380	0.0006	0.0000	0.0034	0.5722	0.0100

	2	0.4214	0.3422	0.2364	0.0730	0.2200	0.0006	0.0474	0.0006	0.6491	0.0092
BNP PARIBAS ESPAÑA	1	0.1723	0.2901	0.5376	0.0606	0.0983	0.0644	0.0347	0.3832	0.0596	0.2992
	2	0.1723	0.2901	0.5376	0.0606	0.0983	0.0644	0.0347	0.3832	0.0596	0.2992
Min.(2)		0.0003	0.0003	0.0003	0.0001	0.0003	0.0003	0.0002	0.0002	0.0003	0.0002
Máx.(2)		0.7761	0.9995	0.6771	0.6212	0.5788	0.4427	0.9572	0.7264	0.7201	0.4007
Media (2)		0.2553	0.3594	0.3853	0.1198	0.1466	0.1288	0.1360	0.2266	0.1344	0.1077
Desv. Est. (2)		0.2329	0.2397	0.1962	0.1395	0.1731	0.1398	0.2403	0.2380	0.2143	0.1197

In order to compare the virtual weights from the three approaches, we used the non-parametric Friedman test for several related samples and the results are shown in Table 5. The hypothesis of difference can not be rejected for three virtual variables: depreciation expenses, other management expenses and portfolio of securities. The Wilcoxon test for two related samples are shown in Table 6 (SE-ADU compares the virtual variables from super-efficiency model and from Adu's approach; SE-Cooper *et al.* compares the virtual variables from super-efficiency model and from Cooper *et al.*'s approach; Adu- Cooper *et al.* compares the virtual variables from Adu's approach and from Cooper *et al.*'s approach).

Table 5. Friedman Test

	F test	p-value
PE_I	15.672	.000
DE_I	3.351	.187
OME_I	2.703	.259
T_O	10.029	.007
CL_O	4.235	.120
PF_O	5.622	.060
D_O	19.500	.000
DCEA_O	11.169	.004
DCEL_O	11.378	.000
C_O	15.500	.000

(in bold statistically significant differences $p = .05$)

Table 6. Wilcoxon test p –value

	SE-Adu	SE-Cooper <i>et al.</i>	Adu- Cooper <i>et al.</i>
PE_I	.028	.717	.001
DE_I	.163	.658	.171
OME_I	.492	.546	.687
T_O	.074	.040	.879
CL_O	.657	.376	.936
PF_O	.266	.717	.022
D_O	.499	.126	.002
DCEA_O	1.000	.018	.033
DCEL_O	.028	.469	.018
C_O	.018	.147	.064

(in bold statistically significant differences $p = .05$)

4. Conclusions

Multiplier DEA models have a serious limitation because the extreme efficient DMUs usually have associated multiple sets of optimal weights. Adu (2001) and Cooper *et al.* (2007) proposed

two different approaches in order to select a set of weight according to a reasonable criterion. Besides, the super-efficiency DEA model, which identifies extreme efficient DMUs in an easy way, only generates a unique set of weights.

Although the previous proposals have different basis, the comparison of the virtual weights from the three previous approaches shows that the difference is not statistically significant for all the variables when the previous models are applied in the Spanish banking sector, even though Cooper *et al.* (2007)'s approach always get positive virtual values, unlike the other two ones.

References

Andersen. P. and N. Petersen (1993). A Procedure for Ranking Efficient Units in Data Envelopment Analysis. *Annals of Operational Research* 116 (1-4), 225-242.

Adu, L.M. (2001). *A Data Envelopment Analysis-Based Framework for Strategic Group Analysis: Empirical Investigation in the Hospital Industry*. PhD Thesis. University of Iowa.

Charnes, A., W.W. Cooper y R.M. Thrall (1991). A Structure for Classifying and Characterizing Efficiencies and Inefficiencies in DEA. *Journal of Productivity Analysis* 2, 197-237.

Cooper. W.W.; J.L. Ruiz. and I. Sirvent (2007). Choosing Weights from Alternative Optimal Solutions of Dual Multiplier Models in DEA. *European Journal of Operational Research* 180 (1), 443–458.

Li, X.B. y G.R. Reeves. (1999). A Multiple Criteria Approach to Data Envelopment Analysis. *European Journal of Operational Research* 115, 207-517.

Lozano-Vivas, A., J.T. Pastor. y J.M. Pastor (2002). An Efficiency Comparison of European Banking Systems Operating under Different Environmental Conditions. *Journal of Productivity Analysis* 18, 2002.

Nacif, N.B., Soares de Mello, J.C.C and Angulo-Meza, L. (2009) Choosing Weights in Optimal Solutions for DEA-BCC Models by means of a n-dimensional Smooth Frontier, *Pesquisa Operacional* 29 (3), 623-642.

Olesen, O.B. and N.C. Petersen (2003). Identification and Use of Efficient Faces and Facets in DEA. *Journal of Productivity Analysis* 20, 323-360.

Pastor, J.M., F. Pérez and J. Quesada (1997). Efficiency analysis in banking firms: An international comparison. *European Journal of Operational Research* 98, 395-407.

Prior, D. and J. Surroca (2006). Strategic Groups Based on Marginal Rates: An Application to the Spanish Banking Industry. *European Journal of Operational Research* 170, 293-314.

Roll, Y., W. Cook and B. Golany. (1991). Controlling Factor Weights in Data Envelopment Analysis. *IIE Transactions* 23, 2-9.

Rosen, D., C. Schaffnit and J.C. Paradi. (1998). Marginal Rates and Two-dimensional Level Curves in DEA. *Journal of Productivity Analysis* 9, 205-232.

Sexton, T. R., R. H. Silkman and A. J. Hogan (1986). "Data Envelopment Analysis: Critiques and Extensions." In R.H. Silkman's, *Measuring Efficiency: An Assessment of Data Envelopment Analysis* San Francisco, California: Jossey-Bass.

Thrall, R. (1996). The lack of Invariance of Optimal Dual Solutions under Translation. *Annals of Operations Research* 66, 103-108.

Wilson, P.W. (1995). Detecting Influential Observations in Data Envelopment Analysis. *Journal of Productivity Analysis* 6, 27-46.

